

Synthesis of 4-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) Benzoic acid Hydrazide, 3-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) Benzoic acid Hydrazide, 4-(N,1-Naphthylsulfonamido) Benzoic acid Hydrazide and their Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents

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The esters of 4-(4'-bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid and 3-(4'-bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid were converted to the hydrazides and N-benzylidene derivatives prepared using few aldehydes. 4-(N,1-naphthylsulfonamido) benzoic acid was prepared by condensing 1-naphthylamine with *p*-bromobenzene sulfonyl chloride. The bromo group was replaced by the cyano group and subsequently hydrolysed to the acid. From the hydrazide of the above acid N-benzylidene derivatives were obtained. Both, the hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives, were screened for antibacterial activity.

SINCE the discovery of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) as an effective antitubercular drug, a large number of hydrazides have been synthesised and tested for antibacterial properties¹⁻⁹. Isoxazole carboxylic acid hydrazides have been reported as antileprotic agents¹⁰ and phenothiazine carboxylic acid hydrazides¹¹ possessed anticonvulsant activity. Besides the hydrazides are known to have anthelmintic¹² and antifungal¹³ activity. In view of these observations, it was felt interesting to synthesise a series of hydrazides and their derivatives (Scheme I & II) having sulfonamide moiety for antibacterial screening

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected

4-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid (I)

13.7 g of *p*-aminobenzoic acid and 25.5 g. *p*-bromobenzenesulfonyl chloride¹⁴ were heated under reflux for 1 hr using pyridine (100 ml.) as a base. The mixture was then cooled and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid. The filtered precipitate was washed with water until free of acid and recrystallised from alcohol. M.P. 286°. Yield 60%. (Found : N, 3.81; Br, 22.39; S, 8.86; C₁₃H₁₀O₄NBrS, requires N, 3.93; Br, 22.48; S, 8.99).

4-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (III, Table 1)

An intimate mixture of I (20 g.), thionyl chloride (20 ml.) and absolute methanol (250 ml.) was refluxed for 20-24 hr. Thereafter excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask were cooled

and poured into 350 ml cold water and filtered. The precipitate was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution at 5°-10°. The ester thus obtained was filtered and washed with cold water till the washings are neutral, and dried. This crude ester (II) was used for the next stage without purification (M.P. of the crude ester 183°).

0.1 mole of II, 0.2 mole 95% hydrazine hydrate and 50 ml methanol were taken in a 250 ml flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 hr and excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask was cooled and poured into 200 ml cold water, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Formyl and acetyl derivatives of III (Table 1)

3.7 g III was refluxed with 30 ml formic acid for 6 hr. The formyl derivative separated out on cooling, the contents of the flask was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol.

The acetyl derivative of III was prepared by the usual method using acetic anhydride and acetic acid.

N-Benzylidene 4-(4'-Bromobenzene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazides (IV, Table 2)

Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (III) and a suitable aldehyde were taken in 50 ml ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 1-1½ hr. The product separating on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from acetone.

The above procedures were adopted for 3-amino-benzoic acid to obtain 3-(4'-Bromobenzene sulfonamido) benzoic acid m.p. 235°, methyl ester m.p. 155°, 3-(4'-Bromobenzene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide, its formyl and acetyl derivatives (Table 1).

Scheme I

Scheme II

The *N*-Benzylidene 3-(4'-Bromobenzene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazides are shown in Table 3.

N,1-Naphthyl-4-bromobenzene sulfonamide (V)

14.3 g 1-naphthylamine was condensed with 25.5 g *p*-bromobenzene sulfonyl chloride with pyridine as above. The sulfonamide derivative obtained was recrystallised from alcohol. M.P. 170°. Yield 76%. (Found : N, 3.74; Br, 21.94; S, 8.68; C₁₆H₁₂O₂NBrS requires N, 3.86; Br, 22.10; S, 8.83.)

4-(*N*,1-Naphthylsulfonamido) benzoic acid (VI)

23.2 g V was dissolved in 50 ml dimethylformamide, to which 13.6 g cuprous cyanide was added. The mixture was refluxed for 10–12 hr in an oil bath. Thereafter the mixture was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and heated further for 2 hr.

The acid separating on cooling was filtered and washed with water. The compound thus obtained was purified by dissolving it in saturated sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitated with acid. The precipitate was filtered, washed well with water and recrystallised from alcohol, M.P. 283°, yield 52%.

4-(*N*,1-Naphthylsulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (VII), its formyl and acetyl derivatives (Table 1), *N*-Benzylidene 4-(*N*,1-Naphthylsulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (Table 4) were prepared according to the above procedure.

Screening for antibacterial activity

The compounds listed in Tables 1–4 have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were as follows : *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia*

TABLE-1

	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %		
				Calcd.	Found	
1. 4-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (III)	244-45	81	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ BrS	C,	42.16	41.94
				H,	3.20	3.26
				N,	11.35	11.23
				Br,	21.62	21.46
				S,	8.64	8.60
2. Acetyl	256	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	N,	10.20	10.04
				Br,	19.42	19.36
				S,	7.76	7.61
3. Formyl	283	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	N,	10.55	10.49
				Br,	20.10	20.16
				S,	8.04	7.86
4. 3-(4'-Bromobenzenesulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide	221	78	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ BrS	C,	42.16	42.01
				H,	3.20	3.14
				N,	11.35	11.20
				Br,	21.62	21.51
				S,	8.64	8.58
5. Acetyl	201	64	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	N,	10.20	10.12
				Br,	19.42	19.31
				S,	7.76	7.69
6. Formyl	238	76	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	N,	10.55	10.42
				Br,	20.10	20.02
				S,	8.04	8.09
7. 4-(N,1-Naphthylsulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (VII)	210-11	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	C,	59.81	59.93
				H,	4.39	4.32
				N,	12.31	12.19
				Br,	21.62	21.51
				S,	9.38	9.22
8. Acetyl	236	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	N,	10.96	10.87
				S,	8.35	8.21
9. Formyl	269	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S	N,	11.39	11.20
				S,	8.67	8.53

TABLE 2—N-BENZYLIDENE 4-(4'-BROMOBENZENESULFONAMIDO) BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES (IV)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %					
					N		S		Br	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
10.	C ₆ H ₅	255	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ BrS	9.16	9.04	6.98	6.70	17.47	17.38
11.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	280	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ BrS	11.19	11.26	6.39	6.28	15.99	15.83
12.	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	289	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.86	8.74	6.75	6.59	16.89	16.81
13.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	270	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.86	8.79	6.75	6.81	16.89	16.76
14.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	251	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.60	8.69	6.56	6.43	16.40	16.34
15.	2-Furyl	260	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	9.37	9.21	7.14	6.98	17.85	17.80

TABLE 3—N-BENZYLIDENE 3-(4'-BROMOBENZENE SULFONAMIDO) BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %					
					N		S		Br	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
16.	C ₆ H ₅	195	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ BrS	9.16	9.09	6.98	6.81	17.47	17.52
17.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	230	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ BrS	11.19	11.11	6.39	6.22	15.99	15.88
18.	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	198	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.86	8.69	6.75	6.64	16.89	16.73
19.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	250	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.86	8.73	6.75	6.69	16.89	16.68
20.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	203	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	8.60	8.56	6.56	6.39	16.40	16.29
21.	2-Furyl	160	58	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ BrS	9.37	9.17	7.14	6.94	17.85	17.76

TABLE 4—N-BENZYLIDENE 4-(N, 1-NAPHTHYSULFONAMIDO) BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES(VIII)

No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
					N		S	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
22.	C ₆ H ₅	258	58	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.78	9.65	7.45	7.36
23.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	263	69	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	11.81	11.86	6.75	6.58
24.	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	297	52	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ S	9.43	9.31	7.19	7.09
25.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	286	72	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S	9.43	9.33	7.19	7.14
26.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	240	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃ S	9.14	9.00	6.97	6.83
27.	2-Furyl	271	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	10.02	9.81	7.63	7.48

coli, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by ditch plate technique¹⁵, using concentration levels of 200 µg, 1 mg and 3 mg per ml.

Compound Nos. 1, 2, 3, 10–15, and 4, 5, 6, 16–21 completely inhibited the growth of *Staph. aureus* and *B. cereus* at all the concentration levels employed. Compounds 1–3 and 10–15, slightly inhibited the growth of *Shi. flexneri*, while compounds 4–6, 16–21, completely inhibited the growth of the same organism. Compound Nos. 7–9, and 22–27, slightly inhibited the growth of *Staph. aureus* and *B. cereus* at the concentration of 200 µg/ml while the same organisms were completely inhibited at the concentration levels of 1 mg and 3 mg per ml. These compounds slightly inhibited the growth of *Shi. flexneri*.

Ps. aeruginosa was slightly inhibited at all the concentration levels of all the compounds tested. None of the compounds (1–27) were effective against *E. coli* and *S. typhi*.

In general all the compounds tested were found to be more effective against gram-positive bacteria than gram-negative bacteria.

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References

1. T. RINDERSPACHER and B. PRIJS, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 22.
2. A. WINTERSTEIN, B. HEGEDUS, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 39, 229.
3. W. WERNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1333.
4. A. L. MINOZHAYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1966, 19, 793; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 539432.
5. O. ISLER, H. GUTMANN, O. STRAUB, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 38, 1033, 1046.
6. K. U. M. PRASAD, B. H. IYER and M. SIRSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 784.
7. S. S. PARMAR and R. KUMAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 635.
8. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 763.
9. S. BAHADUR, A. K. GOEL and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 526.
10. T. S. GARDENER, E. WENIS and . . LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1514.
11. SWISS, 419, 136, 1967; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 29709c.
12. R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 706.
13. BRIT, 1,085,474, 1967; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 95567f.
14. C. S. MARVEL and F. E. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2696.
15. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", 3rd Ed., Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.